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A meshfree-based modelling approach for predicting the effective properties of AP-PLY composite laminates

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Outline

- Research background and aim
- Challenges in modelling AP-PLY composites
- Meshfree-based modelling approach
- Results and discussion
- Summary

1. Research background and aim

- Development of the world's largest composite fan to support Rolls-Royce's strategy of offering next generation of gas turbine engines for civil airplanes
- A single piece engine containment case that is based on carbon fibre composite materials and fan-blade off capable needs to be designed and manufactured

Industrial partners

Rolls-Royce UltraFan

1. Research background and aim

- Advanced placed ply (AP-PLY) composite materials (also known as interleaved composites) to be employed to manufacture this type of engine containment case
 - Tape based nature → automated manufacturing → massive production of large structures
 - Woven-like construction → layer connectivity → good impact and delamination resistance

A full ply set

A 3-layer sequence

Tape connectivity across the thickness direction

1. Research background & aim

- **Research problem:** how the internal architecture and layup design of AP-PLY composites affect the macroscopic properties (which is hard to address by performing experimental trials)
 - Typical design parameters include tape orientations, width, thickness and skip distance (step size)
 - Typical output parameters include elastic properties, material strengths, impact performance, etc.
- **Research aim:** develop a numerical model to understand the effect of the internal architecture and layup design on the macroscopic behaviour
 - Prediction of the elastic properties as a start point
 - Prediction of impact behaviour as the ultimate goal

2. Challenges in modelling AP-PLY composites

- Stacking details of the AP-PLY composites

(a) A laminate (12 ply sets)

(b) A ply set (4 sequences)

(c) A sequence (3 layers)

- A large number of very thin tapes
 - Layer of tapes: 144 layers
 - Nominal tape thickness: 0.27 mm
- Large unit cell size due to large tape width and skip distance
 - Tape width: 75 mm;
 - Skip distance: 300 mm
 - Tape orientations: $-60^\circ/0^\circ/60^\circ$
 - Unit cell (UC) size: 600 mm x 350 mm

2. Challenges in modelling AP-PLY composites

- Complicated geometrical interactions among tapes
 - Thickness of a ply set before consolidation:
3.24 mm
 - Thickness of a ply set after consolidation:
0.81 mm
 - Tape geometries vary from layer to layer
 - The complexity increases significantly after stacking only a few layers

3. Meshfree-based modelling approach

- Introduction to meshfree methods (or meshless methods)
 - Node-based discretisation, no elements needed to construct a domain
 - Explicit generation of the geometrical details of the domain can be avoided

3. Meshfree-based modelling approach

- Identification of material points in different tapes of AP-PLY composite materials
 - Material type and location (which tape)
 - Orientations (longitudinal + transverse)
 - Facts revealed by reproducing the layup process
 - Tape portions in the inner areas of hexagons and triangles are straight
 - Undulations of a tape occur on the boundary lines not parallel to the fibre direction
 - Magnitude of undulation in any position equals to the nominal thickness of a tape
 - The effective thickness of a ply set (12 layers) after consolidation is 3-layer thick

3. Meshfree-based modelling approach

- Material orientations of the wavy portions

Two assumptions for the wavy portions

- 1) No volume change after consolidation
- 2) Constant undulation in the wavy portion

3. Meshfree-based modelling approach

- Elasticity matrix in the global coordinate system
 - Location of nodes in tapes and their orientations
 - Tapes are transversely isotropic composites

$$\mathbf{C}^g = (\mathbf{T}^{g|l})' \mathbf{C}^l \mathbf{T}^{g|l}$$

\mathbf{C}^l — Elasticity matrix in LCS

\mathbf{C}^g — Elasticity matrix in GCS

$\mathbf{T}^{g|l}$ — Transformation matrix

$$\mathbf{C}^l = \begin{bmatrix} C_{11} & C_{12} & C_{12} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ C_{12} & C_{22} & C_{23} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ C_{12} & C_{23} & C_{22} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & C_{44} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & C_{55} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & C_{44} \end{bmatrix}$$

3. Meshfree-based modelling approach

- Implicit implementation of the internal architecture of AP-PLY composite materials for numerical prediction of the effective elastic properties
 - Discretise the unit cell with field nodes & integration points
 - Calculate the shape functions of each integration point
 - Calculate the nodal stiffness matrix for each integration point, \mathbf{K}_{ij}
 - The location and orientation of this integration point
 - The elasticity matrix in the global coordinate system
 - Assemble to form the global stiffness matrix, \mathbf{K}
 - Solve the system equation for given boundary conditions, $\mathbf{KU} = \mathbf{F}$
 - Displacement of all field nodes, \mathbf{U}
 - Strains of all integration points, $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}$
 - Stresses of all integration points $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$
 - Compute the effective properties of composites, $\int \boldsymbol{\sigma} dV = \mathbf{C}^{eff} \int \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} dV$

4. Results and discussion

- A numerical example using the proposed approach will be presented

5. Summary

- Research background and aim
 - A need for developing AP-PLY composite based fan case
 - A predictive tool for understanding AP-PLY composites
- Challenges in modelling AP-PLY composites
 - Large number of thin tapes and large unit cell size
 - Highly complicated geometrical interactions among tapes
- Meshfree-based modelling approach
 - Analytical identification of the locations and orientations of tapes
 - Implicit implementation of the internal architecture for numerical analysis
- Results and discussion
 - To be updated